

The Environmental Audit and its Implementation in Industries: A Case Study of Shri Vitthal Sahakri Karkhana Venunagar, Pandharpur

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Introduction:

In the 21st century the whole world is facing the different environmental problem global climate change, reduction in the ozone layer, increasing toxic wastes, loss of land loss or organic species; environmental Audit and it's implementation in sugar industries.

Environmental audit is a system for a integrating the interest of the industry and the supportive. The environmental audit is envisaged to become apart of every industry's internal procedure so as to help the industry in fulfilling it's responsibilities to words better environment.

Today's unbalanced environmental conditions the govts of all over the world setting every stricter norms for industries to achieve better pollution control. The concept of environmental audit has emerged as a self-exercise for every industries and has been mandatory in India. The notification of environmental audit carried under environmental protection rule, 1986 issued on April 22, 1993. Industries to submit an environmental audit for each financial year in form – v to the concerned stat pollution control boards on or before sept. 30th every year begging 1993. The environmental audit occupies two important acts e.g. water prevention and control of pollution of environmental audit is a management tool comprising systematic, documented periodic and objective evaluation of how well the management of an industry is performing in terms waste prevention and reduction, assessing compliance with regulatory requirement; facilitating control of environmental practices by industry management and pacing environmental information in the public domain.

The excess usages of raw material unless recorded, finds its way in to the environment causing pollution wastes from an industry includes non-product discharges in various gaseous, liquid and solid which all are comprising in environmental audit statement many times the top management of a company may not be aware of the ground requites of the company and much more specific to environmental pollution control for the environmental audit proves as a bridge in between management of industries and pollution control authority.

For Checking out actual implementation of environmental audit statement the Shri Vitthal Shakari Karkhana Venunagar, Pandharpur environmental audit used as geographical any sties Shri Vitthal Shakari Karkhana Venunagar, Pandharpur submit their yearly environmental audit statement to Maharashtra

pollution control board (MPCB) for getting consent. The Shri Vitthal Shakari Karkhana Venunagar, Pandharpur environmental audit statement is in form- V it comprises water and raw material consumptions in detail pollution discharged to environment in detail pollution discharged to environment per unit of out put hazardous waste and waste disposal, pollution control strategies along with other particulars for improving acuity of environment.

Environmental auditing for has for benefits to the industry, to the society and natural at large environmental audit identification of potential cost saving which can be accrued

reeducation in raw material consumption by way of waste and adaptation of recycle, recovery in pollution load.

Objective

1. To compare the environmental audit with financial audit.
2. To find out procedure of formation and submission of environmental audit.
3. To asses various contents of environmental audit.
4. To criticize the environmental audit and pollution control.
5. To demarcate the various benefits of environmental audit.

Data base and methodology

The study is based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected by regular visits Shri Vitthal Shakari Karkhana Venunagar, Pandharpur for analyzing their pollution control facilities and effluent irrigated land.

The related secondary data obtained in Shri Vitthal Shakari Karkhana Venunagar, Pandharpur published and unpublished documents.

Discussion

The environmental audit is not as like a financial audit. The purpose of financial audit is not merely to detect fraudulent expenditure but, more importantly to eliminate wasteful expenditure live wish environmental audit is aimed at benefiting the industry as much as the environment. Some of the important feature of financial audit and important feature of financial audit and environmental audit are compared in (Table No. 1)

Table No. 1 Comparison of financial audit environment . Audit

Sr. No.	Aspects	Financial audit	environment audit
1.	It safe guards against	Extravagance carelessness,, fraud.	Excess inputs unrelated raw materials waste pollution.
2.	Which reflects in	Monitory losses	Monitory losses harm to environment.
3.	Audits objectives	Regular prudent expenditure	A good acuity
4.	Audit needs emanation of	Books	Inventory records in detail.
5.	To verify financial	Financial	Environmental
6.	What should be proper	Balance sheet	Input, out put material balance sheet.
7.	It gives safety for	Good financial condition	Sustainable resources utilization.

As compare to environmental audit with financial audit the important objective is to keep a good environmental duality.

There are various aspects asses for making environmental audit statement following diagram reflects the various industries aspects reburied for envt. audit.

Fig. 1 A typical Diagram various aspects of environmental Audit.

For studying actual environmental audit statement of Shri Vitthal Shakari Karkhana Venunagar, Pandharpur environmental audit statement referred. The environmental audit statement is only for sugar industry. The part A of environmental audit statement give the information about names and address of that industry, industry code. The Shri Vitthal Shakari Karkhana Venunagar, Pandharpur sugar factory, capacity 8000 tones cone crushed per day and other information.

The Shri Vitthal Shakari Karkhana Venunagar, Pandharpur environmental audit statement part-B having details of water and raw material consumption.

Table No. 2 Water consumption (CUM)

Sr. No.	Operations	Year (2016-2017)	Year (2017-2018)
1	Process	900	850
2	Cooling	550	520
3	Domestic	160	170

Source: Shri Vitthal Shakari Karkhana Venunagar, Pandharpur

The high amount of water used for processing, cooling and domestics purpose in 2017-2018-and 2016-17 water consumption are same.

Table No. 3 Process water consumption as product out put.

Sr. No.	Name of the product	Process water consumption per product out put (Lit/KG of sugar produced)	
		Year 2016-17	Year 2017-2018
1	Sugar	1.26	1.26

Source:Shri Vitthal Shakari Karkhana Venunagar, Pandharpur

The 1.26 liters of process water used per K.G. of sugar produced in 2016-17 as compare to 2017-18 is the 1.25 lit of process water required for 1 Kg of sugar produced.

Table No. 4 Water consumption in lit. per MT of sugar crushed.

Sr. No.	Particulars (Lit/MT of sugar cane crushed)	Year (2016-2017)	Year (2017-2018)	National ave. 8000 TCD (Lit/MT)
1	Process water	180	170	236
2	Cooling water	110	104	161

Source: Shri Vitthal Shakari Karkhana Venunagar, Pandharpur

The water consumption for processing of Shri Vitthal Shakari Karkhana Venunagar, Pandharpur has 180 lit, and 170 Lit. of water used per MT sugarcane crushing in 2016-17 and 236 lit/MT (500 TCO)

Table No. 5 Power consumption.

Sr. No.	Particulars	Year (2016-2017)	Year (2017-2018)	National average
1	Power consumption KWH/MT of cane crushed	16.40	17.25	22.00

Source: Shri Vitthal Shakari Karkhana Venunagar, Pandharpur

The 16.40 KWH of power used in 2017-18 per metric tones (MT) of cane crushed. These value is lowers that national average vi 2. 22 KWH power used per MT of sugar cane crushed.

Table No. 6 Effluent generated per metric tones (MT)cane crushed.

Sr. No.	Particulars	Year (2016-2017)	Year (2017-2018)
1	Lit/ Mt of sugar cane crushed	92.50	74.18
2	Lit/ quintal sugar produced	83.20	82.60

Source:Shri Vitthal Shakari Karkhana Venunagar, Pandharpur

The above table reflects 92.50 lit, and 96.53 lit effluent generated per metric tones (MT) of sugar cane crushed in year 2016-17 and 2017-18 respective. The 83.20 lit and 82.60 lit of effluent generate per quintal of sugar menu factored.

Table No. 7 Pollution discharged

Sr. No.	Particulars	Quantity cam/day	Concentration	Concentration discharged (Mass/day)
1.	Waste water	530	88 mg/lit	48.7 kg/day
2.	Air stack 1 (Spm)	1946301	110 mg/nm3	191 kg/day
	stack 2	3574216	89 mg/nm3	325 kg/day
	stack 3	3592543	1.17 mg/nm3	429 kg./day
3.	Noise dB	N.A	45-50	-

Source: Shri Vitthal Shakari Karkhana Venunagar, Pandharpur

The table no. 7 show the reflects the various pollutants and its concentrations. The waste water bio-chemical oxygen demand (BOD) concentration is 88 mg/lit and mass concentration is 48.7 kg./day in Air pollution suspended particulate matter (spm) concentration in various according to stack. The stack 1, 2, 3, SPM mass concentration are 194 kg/day 329 kg/day, 432 kg/day respectively. The noise level is around. 45.50 DB. The air pollution level is much lowers than MCPB standards .

Table No. 8 solid water and its Re-using

Sr. No.	Solid water	Total quantity in tones	
		Year 2017-2018	Year 2017-2018
1	From pollution control facilities		
	1. Oil and gases	3.9	3.1
	2. Biological sludge	5.7	4.9
	3. Fly ash.	2199	1750
2	Quantity recycled		
	i. Bagasse	142922	101212
	ii. Presumed	21292	16971
	iii. Fly ash	2127	1820
	iv. oil and grease	4.2	2.9

Source: Shri Vitthal Shakari Karkhana Venunagar, Pandharpur

The above table no. 8 reflects the various amounts of solid waste generated and recycled. Mostly bagasse is recycled used as fuel for energy generation in boiler. The all press mud used as fuel and burns in boiler.

Table No. 9 Effluent Analysis report

Sr. No.	Parameters	Untreated	Treated
1	PH	4.02-4.45	6.4-7.2
2	COD	2722-9106	2.30-400
3	BOD	820-4000	95-1000
4	TB	3000-4200	770-1520
5	TDB	1700-3720	1400-2030
6	SS	80-50	50-100
7	Chlorides	45-1900	55-99
8	Oil and grease	15-30	Nil

Source: Shri Vitthal Shakari Karkhana Venunagar, Pandharpur

The show table no. 9 the waste water (Pandharpur untreated and treated analysis report. According to Maharashtra pollution control board SCMPCB) the treated effluent characteristics is favourable for irrigation. The framers near vicinity of industry area use the effluent for irrigation.

Table No. 10 Ambient air quality in sugar mill area

Sr. No.	Stations	SPM 9/NM3	NOX 9/NM3	So2 9/NM3
1	Sugar gate	1284.200	21.7-24.9	6.3-7.5
2	Weighing bridge	245	27	8.7
3	Distillery gate	187	14	4.7
4	Bio-gas site	195	20.7	7.2

Source: Shri.Vitthal Shakari Karkhana Venunagar, Pandharpur

In ambient air the pollutions concentration at sugar sate, weighing bridge, distillery gate and biogas site SPM (suspended particulate matter), NOX (Oxides of nitrogen) so2 (sulpher di oxides). The SPM, NOX, SO2, Concentrations are lower than standards norms

Conclusion

As environmental audit helps in pollution and improved production, safely health, and conservation of natural resources, it's overall objectives can be stated as achieving sustainable development. The Shri Vitthal Shakari Karkhanka, Venunagar, Pandharpur. Water consumption, power consumption is lower than national average. The treated waste water, viz effluent characteristics is suitable for use in irrigation the farmers use this effluent for irrigation.

The environmental audit proves as an integrated approach for conserving natural resources and controlling pollution.

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